

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
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14th May, 1973.

Dear Andrew,

Several points. This morning I got the Provisional Programme for the Arabian Seminar and hope to be along on the Thursday. I cannot however manage Friday as I have CBA meetings throughout the day. I wondered whether you would be able to let me know what Bibby has to say about the Seleucid period since it is likely to arise on Qatar, and would you also note anything new which Tosi may say in regard to Iran and Oman. I imagine that you'll be making notes on the latter for your own purposes so I hope it won't be too much trouble to pop a carbon in for me if you type your notes.

I heard last week that I have got a British Academy grant for Oman, though not quite as much as I'd sought, and since I do not make a practice of over-costing, it means that any material help you can put my way to lessen expenses will be doubly welcome if permission is given.

As regards my full report on the Musandam and northern Oman, it occurred to me belatedly to ask whether it might be useful to you to contribute a section on any aspect of relevance. East & West has agreed to publish but has set no limits as to length. Falcon's report on the geology has appeared briefly so I need do no more than refer to it, and Claudio Vita-Finzi is providing a section on the geomorphology of the area. I invited Dr. Ann Coles to consider a note on the social geography but apart from initial interest, I don't know what she has decided. I have completed the gazetteer and the description of the pottery should be ready by next month. Which leaves me with the general introduction still to write. It occurred to me to wonder if you had anything appropriate which could be published as a section in your name but in the same report since its useful to have the information between one cover? Documentary sources for the area or conclusions based on your Minab survey were the points that sprang to mind. Although generous with space, E. & W. are slow, and the Editor never seems to keep to schedule, but space rather than speed seemed to me to be preferable. Anyway, please let me have your reactions.

Yours,

Andrew Williamson, Esq., M.A.,
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Woodstock, Oxon.

B. De Cardi